

INVESTIGATION FOR GENETIC VARIABILITY FOR GRAIN YIELD AND ITS COMPONENT TRAITS IN SORGHUM (*SORGHUM BICOLOR* (LINN) MOENCH.) GERMPLASM LINES.

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MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised:08.10.2024; MS Accepted:09.10.2024)

MS 3311

(RESEARCH PAPER IN GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING,)

Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to estimate the genetic variability and correlation and to identify potential germplasm lines in Sorghum. 60 germplasm lines along with three checks were sown in a randomized block design with three replications, during Kharif 2023 at field of Agricultural Botany, Dr. PDKV, Akola. The observations were recorded on six characters viz., days to 50 % flowering, plant height (cm), days to maturity, panicle length (cm), panicle breadth (cm) and grain yield per plant (g/plant). Analysis of variance and mean performance revealed highly significant difference among the all genotypes for all the traits studied indicating the presence of considerable amount of genetic variability. Moderate to high estimates for GCV and PCV were observed for the characters, plant height (cm), panicle length (cm), panicle breadth (cm), grain yield per plant (g/plant), 100-seed weight (g), grain density (g/ml), fodder yield (g/plant), zinc (ppm), iron (ppm), phytic acid (mg/g) and inorganic phosphorous (mg/g). High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for all the characters except days to 50 % flowering and days to maturity indicating that all these characters were governed by additive genes and selection will be rewarding for the improvement of such traits. Based on mean performance of the germplasm lines. The five germplasm lines EC0487700, EC0487398, EC0487685, IC0409374 and IC0283892 were recorded significantly superior performance for grain yield per plant. Other yield attributes like panicle length and panicle breadth were also considerably high in these germplasm lines. Hence these can be selected for further evaluation and directly released as variety.

Keywords: Sorghum, Variability, Coefficient of variance, Genetic Advance, Heritability

Introduction

Sorghum, a crop originating from West Africa, was cultivated approximately 7,000 years ago (Murdock 1959, Maiti 1996a). It belongs to the Poaceae family, specifically the sub-family Panicoideae and the tribe Andropogoneae (Price *et al.*, 2005). Within the 16 sub-tribes, Sorgastreae is one, which includes the two genera *EuSorghum* and *Cleistone*. *EuSorghum* is further divided into two sub-sections: *Halepensi*a and *Arundinacca*. The *Arundinacc*ai section is distinguished by its annual plants or tufted perennials that lack rhizomes and have a chromosome count of $2n = 20$. De Wet (1978) classified these as three species: *S. halepense* (Linn) Pers, *S. propinquum* (Kunth) Hitchc, and *S. bicolor* (Linn) Moench. Within *Sorghum bicolor*, there are five races too: bicolor, durra, guinea, kafir and caudatum. The wild types of Sorghum can offer different traits that are useful for breeding.

Aids in determining heritability estimates and anticipated genetic advance for the individual traits. "Agronomic traits' genetic diversity is essential for broadening the crop's gene pool in breeding programs (Ramirez *et al.*, 1998). "Genetic variability is prerequisite in the existing population In order for varietal improvement to occur, genetic diversity must be present within the population. Greater emphasis on germplasm collection and characterization is required due to loss of genetic variability causing genetic erosion for present and future plant breeding programs.

Variability is therefore the key factors, which determine the amount the degree of progress from selection hinges on variability. Correlation studies between yield and its component characters significantly facilitate plant selection. In several instances, examining the extent of character interrelationships is essential. The phenotypic correlations are not reliable indicators of the inherent association between different variables due to their susceptibility to environmental influences. To ensure a reliable and efficient breeding program, it's crucial to determine genotypic correlation coefficients.

Understanding nature, size, and correlation between complex traits like yield and its components aids in enhancing selection efficiency for desirable characteristics. This study calculates and compares the phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation (PCV and GCV). The study focused on heritability, genetic advance, and their correlation. The study of genetic variations in grain yield and its constituent traits across different species and varieties serves as a solid foundation for identifying superior genotypes to boost yield and other agricultural attributes. Grain yield components frequently demonstrate varying correlations with seed yield and with one another. Understanding the relationships among yield contributing traits is

crucial for developing a genotype with the optimal combination. Grain yield can be affected by multiple traits, making selection complicated for breeders.

Material and method

The Germplasm lines were planted at the field of Agricultural Botany, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, 2023. Akola located at latitude 20.42° North and longitude 76.59° East. It is situated at an altitude of 285 m above sea level. The soil at Akola is vertisol, deep black soil to medium deep black soils which is mostly derived from basalt rocks. The soil texture of experimental area was sandy loam with pH of 7.1.

60 Germplasm lines along with three checks of Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) were sown during Kharif, 2023 in Randomized Block Design (RBD) with three replications. Each entry was sown in two rows each of 3 m length with uniform spacing of 45 cm between rows and 15 cm between plants. A basal dose of 40 kg N, 40 kg of P_2O_5 and 40 kg K_2O per hectare was applied. The remaining 30 kg Nha^{-1} was applied as top dressing at knee-high stage (30-40 days old crop). All the necessary package of practices and need based plant protection measures were followed to raise the healthy crop.

The mean values of observations taken for six different yield traits were used for statistical analysis. The following statistical parameters were worked out for presentation of the data on different quantitative attributes. The data was subjected to the following statistical analysis: Analysis of variance, mean performance of genotypes, heritability and expected genetic advance.

Analysis of variance were estimated for the different characters as per the method, suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1967) for Randomized Block Design. Phenotypic and genotypic variance was estimated according to the method given by Lush (1940). Phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation (PCV and GCV) were computed according to Burton and Devane (1953). GCV and PCV values were categorized as low moderate and high values as indicated by Subramanian and Menon (1973). Heritability percentage in broad sense is calculated by the formula as suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955) and the heritability percentage will be categorized as low, moderate and high as given by Robinson *et al.* (1949). Genetic advance was estimated as per the formula proposed by Lush (1949) and Johnson *et al.* (1955) and the range of genetic advance as per cent of mean was classified as suggested by Johnson *et al.* (1955).

Results and discussion

The mean, variability, heritability, genetic advance as percent of mean and correlation coefficient for yield and yield attributing traits were studied with six characters viz., days to 50% flowering, plant height,

days to maturity, panicle length, panicle breadth and grain yield per plant.

Analysis of variance revealed highly significant difference among treatments in respect of all the characters studied. The genetic variability studies indicated that the germplasm lines used in the

present investigation possessed considerable variability which provides sufficient basis for selection. The results are in agreement with Sujatha *et al.* (2017), Laxshmi *et al.* (2020), Deshmukh *et al.* (2021), Vinodhini *et al.* (2022) Begum *et al.* (2023) and Karpe *et al.* (2023).

Table 1. Analysis of variance for various characters in germplasm lines of Sorghum

Sources	Degree of freedom	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle breadth (cm)	Grain yield per plant (g)
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Replications	2	6.54	42.84	9.36	0.72	0.0464	1.50
Treatments	62	30.01**	9494.00**	73.96**	45.67**	11.89**	684.84**
Error	124	8.50	32.93	6.91	2.35	0.5288	2.70

The earliest germplasm line IC0291129 (56.00 days) recorded significantly superior performance over the best check Parbhani Shakti (63.00 days). However germplasm line EC0488353 (72.33 days) recorded maximum days to blooming and recorded late for flowering. The germplasm line EC0489113 (420 cm) exhibited maximum height on the contrary germplasm line IC0291129 (145 cm) exhibited minimum height and found dwarfest among the germplasm lines. Germplasm line IC0589350 (103 days) matured earlier and germplasm line EC0488353 (124.33 days) recorded maximum days to maturity. The maximum panicle length was found in the germplasm line EC0486792 (29.61 cm), while germplasm line EC0874052 had minimum panicle length (9.00 cm). The germplasm line EC0542211 (15 cm) had the maximum panicle breadth however germplasm line IC0291129 (3.47cm) had minimum panicle breadth. The grain yield per plant ranged from germplasm line IC0352548 (12.95g) to germplasm line EC0487700 (65.89g/plant) with the general mean value of 41.41 g/plant. Similar observations were recorded by Chavan *et al.* (2023), Vinodhini *et al.* (2022).

Out of 60 germplasm lines, 11 germplasm lines recorded early maturity than the best check variety, Parbhani Shakti (107 days). The germplasm lines namely IC0589350, IC0291129, IC0291111, IC0409374 and IC0001517 were found superior performance over the best check, Parbhani Shakti (107 days). The similar findings has been reported by Bhagasara *et al.* (2017) and Shubhashini *et al.* (2019) for days to 50 percent flowering and Tomar *et al.* (2012), Deshmukh *et al.* (2021) for days to maturity.

Panicle length, panicle breadth and grain yield per panicle are considered as yield attributes. Among yield attributes more panicle length, more panicle breadth, higher grain yield per plant are desirable. A wide range of variations existing for various yield attributing traits had been reported in Sorghum by Santhiya *et al.* (2021) and Nirosh *et al.* (2021) for panicle length, Kavipriya *et al.* (2020) for panicle breadth and Badigannavar *et al.* (2017) and Bhagasara *et al.* (2017) for grain yield per plant.

Based on mean performance of the germplasm lines. The five germplasm lines EC0487700, EC0487398, EC0487685, IC0409374 and IC0283892 were recorded significantly superior performance for grain yield per plant. Other yield attributes like panicle length and panicle breadth were also considerably high in these germplasm lines. Hence these can be selected for further evaluation and directly released as variety.

Genetic and Phenotypic coefficient of variation, Heritability and Genetic advance

The GCV and PCV were computed to evaluate the material's variability. Understanding the relative extent of heritable and non-heritable variation for all studied characters is of prime importance. The high values of PCV and GCV indicated that improvement of these traits could be possible through direct selection. The estimates of PCV (6.00%) and GCV (4.06%) for days to 50 % flowering were low indicating presence of less amount of variation for this character among germplasm lines studied. The data revealed that the estimated (GCV) and (PCV) for plant height were 19.26 % and 19.36 %, respectively. Days to maturity data showed that the estimated (GCV) and (PCV) were 4.15 % and 4.75 percent. The (GCV) and (PCV) for panicle length were 20.43 % and 21.88 %. The data of panicle breadth revealed that the estimated (GCV) and (PCV) were 30.43 % and 32.48 %. The data revealed that the estimated (GCV) and (PCV) for grain yield per plant were 36.41 % and 36.63 %, respectively.

Similar results were recorded by the similar kind of high estimates of variability were reported by Kavipriya *et al.* (2020) for panicle breadth. Bhagasara *et al.* (2017), Meena *et al.* (2017), Mohamad *et al.* (2017), Ranjith *et al.* (2017), Sujatha *et al.* (2017) , Santhiya *et al.* (2021) and Arvinth *et al.* (2021) for grain yield. Comparatively high estimates of variability observed in the above characters especially panicle breadth, grain yield per plant shows that there is ample scope of selection. The phenotypic and genotypic coefficient calculated for six traits were listed in Table 2.

Figure.1 Genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for six characters in 60 germplasm lines along with three checks

s	Characters	Mean	Range		Coefficient of Variation (%)		Heritability broad sense (%)	Genetic advance as % of mean
			Min.	Max.	PCV (%)	GCV (%)		
1	Days to 50% flowering	65.94	56.00	72.33	6.00	4.06	45.75	5.66
2	Plant height (cm)	291.52	145.00	420.00	19.36	19.26	98.97	39.48
3	Days to maturity	113.80	103.33	124.33	4.75	4.15	76.40	7.48
4	Panicle length (cm)	19.59	9.00	29.61	20.92	19.4	86.02	37.07
5	Panicle breadth (cm)	6.40	3.47	15.00	32.48	30.43	87.76	58.72
6	Grain yield per plant (g)	41.41	12.95	65.89	36.63	36.41	98.83	74.57

Table 2. Estimation of genetic parameters: variability, heritability and genetic advance as percent of mean in the Sorghum germplasm lines

Figure.2 Broad sense heritability and genetic advance as percent of mean for six characters in 60 germplasm lines along with three checks

The characters plant height and panicle length shows moderate to high GCV and PCV values indicating the presence of considerable amount of variation for this character. Narrow range of value between GCV and PCV indicating less influence of environment for this trait. These observations were in the conformity with the findings of Gedifew *et al.* (2012), Dhutmal *et al.* (2014), Khandelwal *et al.* (2015), Subhashini *et al.* (2019) for plant height. Navya *et al.* (2021), Badigannavar *et al.* (2017), Kassahun *et al.* (2017), Mohamad *et al.* (2017), Sujatha *et al.* (2017) for panicle length.

High heritability (98.97 %) coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean (39.48) were obtained for plant height. High heritability (76.40 %) coupled with low genetic advance as percent of mean (7.48 %) was observed for days to maturity. High heritability (86.02 %) coupled with high genetic advance as percent of mean (37.07 %) was observed for panicle length. However high heritability (87.76 %) accompanied with high genetic advance as percent of mean (58.72 %) were observed for panicle breadth indicate that phenotypic selection may be effective due to presence of additive gene action. High heritability (98.83 %) accompanied with high genetic advance as percent of mean (74.57 %) were obtained for the grain yield per plant.

Moderate heritability (45.75 %) accompanied with low genetic advance as percent of mean (5.66 %) for days to 50 % flowering and heritability (76.40 %) coupled with low genetic advance as percent of mean (7.48 %) was observed for days to maturity. The results were in the agreement with Similar result was observed by Endalamaw and Semahegn (2020), Laxshmi *et al.* (2020), Navya *et al.* (2021), Nirosh

et al. (2021), Santhiya *et al.* (2021) and Begum *et al.* (2023) for plant height.

Conclusion

Based on mean performance of the germplasm lines. The five germplasm lines EC0487700, EC0487398, EC0487685, IC0409374 and IC0283892 were recorded significantly superior performance for grain yield per plant. Other yield attributes like panicle length and panicle breadth were also considerably high in these germplasm lines. Hence these can be selected for further evaluation and directly released as variety. The moderate to high PCV and GCV were observed for plant height, panicle length, panicle breadth and grain yield per plant indicating the existence of more variability for these characters. Low PCV and GCV accompanied with low heritability and genetic advance as percent of mean recorded for days to 50 % flowering and days to maturity indicated that the character is highly influenced by environment. Hence selection would be ineffective for improving these traits selection based on progeny test should be done.

High heritability accompanied with high genetic advance as percent of mean reported for characters *viz.*, plant height, panicle length, panicle breadth, grain yield per plant, suggested predominance of additive type of gene action in controlling these traits and simple selection would be sufficient for these traits to bring genetic improvement in desired direction.

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